

Exploring the Phytochemical Profile and Antibacterial Potency of *Terminalia chebula* through Fruit and Bark Extracts

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are those plants that contain different substances in more than one of their organs that can be utilized for beneficial purposes or that may be an antecedent for the production of valuable medications. Photochemical components may be responsible for the antimicrobial and therapeutic activities of plant classes. This type of revision provides health benefits at a reasonable cost. The current study was planned to evaluate the phytochemical components as well as the abstraction of *T. chebula* using fruit and bark abstracts. The result exposed the existence of medically active compounds in *T. chebula* which are carbohydrates, proteins, phenols, tannins, steroids, flavonoids, saponins, and glycosides. The antibacterial activity of methanol, ethanol, and acetone extracts of *T. chebula* bark and fruit was evaluated by disc diffusion assay using a nutrient broth medium. The methanolic, ethanolic, and acetone extracts of bark and fruit produced significant zones of inhibition against two tested bacteria, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Xanthomonas axonopodis*. The bacteria were found in the range of 2.5 to 9.95 mm/mL. The results of this study revealed the therapeutic prospects of *T. chebula* bark and fruit for the treatment of microbial diseases. Our study results show that *T. chebula* species has great potential for antibacterial activity and can be used as an important source of phytochemicals and antibacterial compounds.

Keywords: Medicine, Plants, Antifungal compounds, Flavonoids

INTRODUCTION

The importance of medicinal plant life for the prevention, remedy, and treatment of illnesses is usually recognized (Umair, 2020; Imtiaz et al., 2023). History discovered that plant life had been a treasured supply of herbal trade-in for retaining human fitness at all times. Their significance is constantly growing day with the aid of using day. Most humans now opt for herbal remedies to conquer critical facet results of much contemporary medication (Owolabi et al., 2007). According to World Health Organization, medicinal plant life will be a high-quality supply to gain several drugs (Nascimento et al., 2000).

In Pakistan, a maximum of human beings opt to take conventional tablets for therapy in their diseases. Keeping in thoughts the growing significance of medicinal flowers to cutting-edge necessities to get new valuable, and simplest reasserts of energetic pharmaceutical ingredients, gift paintings became designed to look at the antibacterial pastime of diverse flowers of Pakistani origin, which can be usually utilized in jape medication and aren't nicely explored (Naqvi et al., 2012). As per approximation among 35,000-70,000 plants species are consumed in people's cures worldwide (Qaiser and Ali, 2009). These harvests offer a critical supply of earnings to a massive variety of rural households. About 70 to 80% of the arena populace use conventional remedies for curing their infection and ailments (Fransworth and Soejarto, 1991). The percentage

of humans the use of conventional remedies reduced in advanced nations (Titz, 2004) because of the provision of fitness facilities.

T. chebula is local to the Indian subcontinent and the adjoining regions consisting of Nepal, the South-West of China and Pakistan stretched to the south as Kerala or maybe Sri Lanka (Chattopadhyay and Bhattacharyya, 2007) *T. chebula* takes place distributed in the forest also combined deciduous forest and covering into forests of relatively dry kinds. In Bio-physical, it limits the Altitude approximately 1500 (-2000) and type of soil is the types of the plant are located on adequately of soil, clayey is also too shady

The antibacterial hobby of *T. chebula* extracts towards numerous bacterial traces was reported. Extracts from special elements of various parts of plants like leaves, roots, flowers, seeds, etc. showcase antibacterial residences that had been implemented on cotton fabric for wound, healthcare care applications (Rathinamoorthy et al., 2014). 33% of total phytoconstituents are hydrolysable tannins (which range 20-50%) and are indictable for pharmacological interest in *T. chebula*. These tannins comprise phenolic carboxylic acid like chebulic acid, Ellagic acid, Gallic acid. Traditionally, plants and animals were used against bacteria (Habib, 2022), virus (Zainab, 2021) and fungus (Kumar et al., 2023) to treat colic pain, persistent cough, sore throat, worried disorders, urinary and kidney disorders, asthma, etc. It is usually used as an anti-diabetic, laxative, digestive, diuretic, and cardio tonic remedy (Chauhan, 2014, Chander ,Khare, 2007). Owing to significant role of this species, a study was planned to evaluate the likely chemicals and antibacterial activity in fruit and barks of *T. chebula* species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

PLANT MATERIAL COLLECTION AND IDENTIFICATION:

The bark and fruit of *T. chebula* were collected from the nursery of Lahore (Patoki). The collected material was identified by the plant expert from the department of forestry in the Islamia University of Bahawalpur. The voucher specimen was deposited in the laboratory of forestry, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur.

CHEMICALS CONSTITUENTS:

Methanol, 200ml distilled water, ethanol, acetone, 0.2% solution of Ninhydrin, 2ml of iodine, 2% solution of FeCl₃, Magnesium ribbon, conc. HCL chloroform, conc. H₂SO₄ was used.

PREPARATION OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF BARK AND FRUIT

First of all, the sample of bark and fruit were washed thoroughly with tap water. The samples were dried in an oven for 24 hours at 70°C. After this, the sample was ground in a high-capacity grinding machine. The coarse sample was sieved in different sizes of sieves. The samples were weighed on the weight machine. A total of 250 gm powder of bark and fruit was put in a glass beaker and then 500 ml of methanol gradually mixed with a stirrer for about 5 to 10 minutes. The prepared solution was covered with aluminium foil for one week. After one week, the samples were filtered through Whitman no. 1 filter paper and the resulting filtrate was air-dried through pores of aluminium foil. After one month, all remaining methanol was evaporated and the extract was obtained in the form of crystals. Now the samples are ready for different tests.

TEST FOR ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *T. CHEBULA* BACTERIAL STRAINS AND GROWTH CONDITIONS

There are two bacterial anxieties which have the name as one is *Bacillus subtilis* (gram-positive bacteria) and another one is *Xanthomonas axonopodis* (negative bacteria) were utilized in antibacterial examining. The analysis way for the development of various bacteria is nutrient agar way. Various Bacterial cultures which is used for anti-microbial test work was developed by picking the different colony from one day ago in agar plates and being suspended in a nutrient chowder moderate for 5 ml solution. All the Cultures were being grown for about 20 hours and regularly shaken at a rate of 200 rpm at a temperature of 28 °C.

DISC DIFFUSION METHOD

For disc dispersion analysis (NARMS, 2002) 1/ml of every bacterial solution was equally spread on the growth medium in the Petri dish. The 6 mm in diameter sterile paper disc, Becton, Dickinson of the diluted plant extract with 10 µL were kept on the surface of agar plates and saturated.

Agar Plates were hatched under proper tilling situations. The Antibacterial process formed a reserve zone around a disc for 24 hours of growth and 2 days of cultivation. Disc drenched with sterile refined water and ethanol helped for control. There are three replicas which is taking place at each concentration.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *T. CHEBULA*

Phytochemical analysis of the test sample was carried out according to standard methods

PLANT EXTRACTS PREPARATION

HOT-WATER EXTRACT

By taking 5mg of fully dry powdered-shape plant substantial and put it in the beaker. 200 ml water was added to the powder. This combination was put on a hot plate for heating purposes with nonstop moving at temp ranging from 30-40°C for 3 hours and 20 minutes. Then the water abstract was filtered with the help of a piece of filter paper and the filtrate was applied for the testing of phytochemical. Water extract was not in us then they kept in the refrigerator.

SOLVENT EXTRACTION

The Crude extract of the plan was arranged by using the Soxhlet extraction technique. In this technique, take 20mg of powdered fruit. This material was equally packed into small thimbles and mined with about 250ml of different dilutions distinctly. Ethanol, acetone, and methanol can be used as solvents. This extraction process. Carried out for around 24 hours until the whole solvent present in the siphon tube of the extractor changed to colourless. Then the extract was transferred to a beaker placed on a hot plate and heated at almost 30-40°C. All the solvent evaporated. The Dried extract was preserved in the refrigerator for their further use in the phytochemical analysis.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS (QUALITATIVE):

Standard techniques were used to check for the presence of bio-active components in the extract.

TEST FOR PROTEINS (NINHYDRIN TEST)

The whole Crude abstract was heated in the presence of Ninhydrin which is 2ml of 0.2% solution. The violet color has seemed which changed into red when more heat confirmed the presence of protein.

TEST FOR PHENOLS

The prepared Crude solution was mixed with FeCl₃ with 2ml of 2% solution. The color changed to blue-green or black which shows the existence of phenols.

TEST FOR TANNINS

The given crude abstract mixed with the solution of FeCl₃ having 2ml of 2% solution. Blue-green or also black colour showed the presence of tannins

TEST FOR FLAVONOIDS (SHINODA TEST)

0.5% of each portion was dissolved in ethanol, warmed and then filtered. Three pieces of Mg chips were added to the filtrate followed by a few drops of conc. HCl. A pink-orange or red-to-purple colouration indicated the presence of flavonoids.

TEST FOR STERIOD

The crude abstract was added with a solution of chloroform having 2ml and pure conc. H₂SO₄ was mixed sidewise. Colour changed into red appeared in the bottom chloroform layer which indicates the existence of steroids. One more test was also performed by adding crude abstract with chloroform which is 2ml. Conc. H₂SO₄ and acetic acid of 2ml of each were added to the solution. The formation of a greenish colouration is an indication of the existence of steroids.

TEST FOR CARBOHYDRATES (IODINE TEST)

The existing crude abstract was added with Iodine of 2ml in quantity. The existence of carbohydrates is indicated by dark blue or purple colouration.

TEST FOR GLYCOSIDES (SALKOWSKI'S TEST)

2ml of chloroform is added to the crude abstract. Then added 2ml chloroform. After that 2ml of conc. H₂SO₄ was added sensibly and shaken slightly. The existence of a steroidal ring indicated if a reddish-brown colour appears i.e. glycone part of the glycoside.

TEST FOR SAPONINS

5ml distil water is added in the following crude abstract in a test tube and shaken forcefully. The existence of saponins is indicated by the formation of stable foam.

RESULTS

The *T. chebula* plant extract of barks and fruits was investigated for qualitative phytochemical screenings and antibacterial properties. These extracted constituents possessed many medicinal, physiological, and pharmacological. In the phytochemical screening of bark extract protein, phenols, tannins, steroids, and glycosides showed positive results while flavonoids, saponins, and carbohydrates were absent. The current study has revealed the presence of phytochemicals and antibacterial properties in the selected sample. The samples of selected tree species were

analyzed in the Laboratories of Pathology and Agriculture of The Islamia University Bahawalpur of Pakistan to explore important phytochemical constituents and antibacterial properties. The current analysis showed that the selected tree species is characterized by the presence of various phytochemicals but the selected samples are devoid of the presence and absence of phytochemicals in each tree part as a result of qualitative analysis.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Phytochemical analysis and antibacterial activity of *T. chebula* extract of fruit and bark; *T. chebula* is local to the Indian sub-continent and the adjoining regions consisting of Nepal the southwest of China and Pakistan stretched to the south as Kerala or may be Sri-Lanka. *T. chebula* plant has a record for use usually in Unani, Ayurveda, and homeopathic remedy because of its extensive spectrum of pharmacological support related to the biologically lively chemical compounds found in this plant. Therefore an attempt was made to evaluate chemical constituents from *T. chebula* fruit and bark. The experimental work is start by extraction of fruit and bark of *T. chebula* with distilled water and Methanol.

B.subtilis and *X.axonopodis* were assayed against all the test of bacteria as a positive control. *T. chebula* are used for the antibacterial test against *B. subtilis* and *X. axonopodis* causing in plants. The extract of the bark of *T. chebula* was used (Table 1).

Table 1: Antibacterial Activities of Bark Extract.

Test organism	Co	EtOH	MeOH	Ace
<i>B.subtilis</i>	2.5±0.01	5.65±0.1	5.6±0.5	5.75±0.2
<i>X.axonopodis</i>	2.5±0.01	5.95±0.1	6±0.5	5.85±0.2

B. subtilis and *X. axonopodis* were assayed against all the tests of bacteria as a positive control. *T.chebula* are used for the antibacterial test against *B.subtilis* and *X.axonopodis* causing in plants ocular. The extract of fruit of *T. chebula* was used (Table 2).

Table 2: Antibacterial Activity of Ethanol and Water Extract of Bark.

Test organism	Co	EtOH	MeOH	Ace
<i>B.subtilis</i>	2.5±0.01	5.975±0.1	6.5±0.5	6.2±0.2
<i>X.axonopodis</i>	2.5±0.01	7.95±0.1	9±0.5	9.95±0.2

Two bacterial strains, namely *Bacillus subtilis* species (+ve bacteria) were used for the testing of antibacterial. The farming/assessment moderate for growth of bacteria is nutrient agar medium. Bacterial cultivars for the testing of antimicrobial which were set by selection of the colony from 24 hours old agar plates and it was suspended in a nutrient growth medium cultivars which were grown aerobically for 24 hours at 28°C.

Antibacterial activity of ethanol and water extract of fruit of *T. chebula* namely *Bacillus subtilis* species (+ve bacteria)

The bacterial strains, namely *Bacillus subtilis* species (+ve bacteria) were utilized for the testing of antibacterial. As the growing medium for the growth of bacteria is the nutrient agar medium. Bacterial cultivars for the testing of antimicrobials which were arranged by gathering the different colonies from 24-hour-old agar dishes suspended in a nutrient growth medium cultivars were grown up aerobically for 24 hours at 28°C.

Antibacterial activity of ethanol and water extract of bark of *T. chebula* against the -ve strain of *Xanthomonas axonopodis*. The bacterial strains, the namely -ve strain of *Xanthomonas axonopodis* was rummage-sale for the testing of antibacterial. The analysed medium for growth of bacteria is the nutrient agar medium. Bacterial cultivars for the different testing of antimicrobial were prepared by selecting different colonies from 24 hours old agar which were suspended in nutrient growth medium cultivars that grew aerobically for 24 hours at 28°C.

Antibacterial activity of ethanol and water extract of the fruit of *T. chebula* against -ve strain of *Xanthomonas axonopodis*. The bacterial strains, namely strain of *Xanthomonas axonopodis* was used for antibacterial testing. The cultivation/assay medium for the growth of bacteria is nutrient agar medium. Bacterial cultivars for antimicrobial testing were prepared by picking colony from 24-hour-old agar plates and it was suspended in a nutrient growth medium cultivars were grown aerobically for 24 hours at 28°C.

QUALITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *T. CHEBULA*

T. chebula enclose different organic composites that are used to deliver certain physiological achievements on human beings and the bioactive substances which include alkaloids, carbohydrates, tannins, phenols, steroids, saponins, and some flavonoids. By using primary as well as secondary metabolism of living organisms, all these mixtures are produced. As concerned with Secondary metabolites which are taxonomically and chemically very miscellaneous compounds having an unclear role.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF FRUIT EXTRACT OF *T.CHEBULA*

In a phytochemical analysis of fruits of *T. chebula* proteins, phenols, Tannins, Flavanoids, Saponins, Steroids and Glycosides content were present But Carbohydrates were absent in methanol extract as indicated in Table (Table 3).

Table 3 Phytochemical analysis of fruit extract of *T. chebula*

Sr. No	Phytochemical	F. Methanol
1	Protein	+ve
2	Phenols	+ve
3	Tannins	+ve
4	Flavanoids	+ve
5	Saponins	+ve
6	Steroids	+ve
7	Carbohydrates	-ve
8	Glycosides	+ve

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF BARK EXTRACT:

In phytochemical analysis of bark of *T. chebula* proteins, Phenols, Tannins, Steroids and Glycosides content was present in methanol extract. The phytochemical analysis of bark of

T.chebula, show that Flavanoids, Saponins and Carbohydrates were absent in methanol extract as indicated in table.

Table 4: Phytochemical analysis of bark extract of *T. chebula*.

S.NO	Phytochemical	B. Methanol
1	Protein	+ve
2	Phenols	+ve
3	Tannins	+ve
4	Flavanoids	-ve
5	Saponins	-ve
6	Steroids	+ve
7	Carbohydrates	-ve
8	Glycosides	+ve

DISCUSSION

T. chebula is a necessary medicinal plant in Indian ordinary medication and it is most frequently used herb in Ayurveda. The dried fruit pulp used to be extracted with ethanol and the residue (1.09%; 4.67g) was once recovered the use of arotary evaporator. The examined bacterial traces confirmed specific patterns of inhibition. The extract confirmed a vast spectrum of antibacterial exercise in opposition to gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. This used to be supported by means of until now find out about on an alcoholic extract that exhibited larger exercise than the aqueous and hexane extracts in opposition to bacteria, with no cell toxicity (Ahmadet al., 1998). The vast spectrum of antibacterial pastime used to be said for *T. chebula* (Phadke and Kulkarni, 1989) and *T. arjuna* (Singh et al., 2008). The ethanol extract at attention of 1 mg/disc confirmed most inhibition against *S. epidermidis*, accompanied by way of *B. subtilis*. Gupta et al. (2002) mentioned that a *T. pallida* fruit methanolic extract confirmed most exercise towards gram-negative bacteria, whilst that of *T. bellerica* confirmed the best inhibition zones towards *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* (Ghosh et al., 2008).

Two chances that may also account for the higher antibacterial recreation of alcoholic extracts are the nature of organic energetic elements (alkaloids, flavonoids, fundamental oil, terpenoids, tannins, etc.), which might also be better in the presence of ethanol; and the enhanced extraction capability of ethanol that can also have yielded an increased range of energetic components accountable for anti-bacterial endeavour (Ghosh et al., 2008). The ethanol extract was once in addition subjected to the broth microdilution technique to decide the MIC (Table 2). The most pastime used to be located towards *S. typhi*, accompanied by way of *S. epidermidis* at an awareness of 1 mg/ml. This result is in settlement with the file of Phadke and Kulkarni (1989) and Rani and Khullar (2004) studied *T. chebula* and *T. arjuna* leaves, respectively. In this study, 90% boom inhibition (IC90) was once located in opposition to *S. epidermidis* and almost 80% boom inhibition used to be located in opposition to *P. aeruginosa* at an awareness of 1 mg/ml

(Figure 1). This existing find out about confirmed antibacterial pastime at a low concentration, whereas Ahmad et al. (1998) stated comparable pastime at an attention of 200 mg/ml. It has been pronounced that the pure compound arjunctin from *T. arjuna* used to be accountable for endeavor towards *S. epidermidis* (Singhet al., 2008).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The plant of *T. chebula* has anti-bacterial properties, and phytochemical analysis (qualitative) of the methanolic extract of the fruit and bark of *T. chebula subtilis* (+ve bacteria and *X. axonopodis* (-ve bacteria) used for antibacterial testing and using bark extract. Since the dawn of time, many medicated plants have been a part and parcel of human society in the fight against various diseases. *T. chebula* is awarded as “the King of Medicine” in Tibet, and it is always at the top of the list of ‘Ayurvedic Materia Drugs’ as it has the unusual power of curing. The overall complete plant consists of highly medicated values and is normally used for the curing of different ailments in people. Terminalia comprises almost 250 different species, which are widely spread in tropical areas of the world (Ammar et al., 2002). In this current exploration, we examined the expected antibacterial potential of the abstracts of the fruit of *T. chebula* for both the Gram-negative and the Gram-positive with multi-drug imperviousness to bacterial pathogens that are too resistant to uropathogenic *E. coli* to illuminate a probable unusual antimicrobial agent from *T. chebula* fruit.

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